

**“Perception of Indigenous Fabrics (Batik) for Casual Wear:
A Study of Undergraduate Students in Abeokuta.”**

by

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CHAPTER ONE

1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background to the Study

The conflict between modernity and tradition is mainstream in contemporary Nigerian society. Over many years, Nigerians have adopted modern lifestyles, habits and institutions without fully setting aside inherited customs and cultural practices. This adaptation process has produced a complex behavioural mix, some of which cannot be clearly described as either modern or traditional (Nigerian Environment Study team, 1991). One area of visible tension is in the clothing choice of young people, particularly students in tertiary institutions.

Casual wear refers to clothing that put comfort and personal expression over formality. It is the relaxed everyday clothing suited for informal setting, and common materials used include cotton, denim, flannel, jersey and polyester. This study focuses specifically on the indigenous textile fabric "batik" and its potential as a casual wear option for undergraduate students in Abeokuta.

Abeokuta is one of the prominent towns in Ogun state, South- Western Nigeria where resist dyeing (adire and batik) method is practiced (Byfield, 2002). It is rather appalling that the use of batik in a land synonymous with large scale indigenous textile market does not reflect much in its cultural display especially in the world of casual wears among university undergraduates.

The technique has deep roots across several cultures and is practised in various forms across South-East Asia, West Africa, and beyond. In recent years, batik has been rarer with a growing interest among younger generation who have used it for personalized everyday clothing like jeans, shorts and trousers.

Batik has served in many social and cultural societies that practice it. Specific designs have historically been used to mark life stages, ceremonies and social status. The use of batik has largely been confined to ceremonial occasions such as burials, naming ceremonies, coronation and traditional marriages as well as household decorative items (Amubode, 2009). Contemporary batik has evolved from its traditional form as clothing to include other use such as accessories, shoes, stationery, bags and home products (Picton, 1995). This evolution means that batik now occupies a bigger cultural space, one that includes the potential for everyday casual wear among younger urban population.

This study investigated how undergraduate students in Abeokuta perceive indigenous textile batik as a fabric for casual wear .

What factors shape their preferences and what steps might encourage wider adoption of locally produced textile in everyday student life.

1.2 Statement of the problem

The major reason for this study was guided by the observation that most tertiary institutions students in Abeokuta do not generally use batik as a casual wear despite the town's long history as the center for

batik and adire production, thereby contributing negatively to the growth and development of the textile industry.

The combination of low patronage of locally manufactured fabric and competition from import has reduced the need to hire more workers, stifled investment, and weakened cultural confidence in indigenous production thus causing great decline in Nigeria's textile industry (Olori, 2003). With the modern technology, skills and delicate designs used in the producing the indigenous fabric to meet the fashion needs of young people, why do they continue to overlook these options?

1.3 Objectives of the study

The broad objective of this study was to examine how undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Abeokuta perceived indigenous textile fabric for casual wears.

The specific objectives were to :

- i. describe the socioeconomic characteristics of the respondents
- ii. assess the perception of students in selected institutions regarding the use of indigenous textile fabric for casual wears.
- iii. identify the form in which they use the fabric.

1.4 Research Questions

The following questions guided the study:

- 1 - what is the socioeconomic characteristics of the respondent?
- 2 - what is the perception of students in the selected institutions regarding use of indigenous textile fabric for casual wears?
- 3 - what is the acceptability level for casual wears among tertiary institutions students?

1.5 Significance of the study

This study contributed to the existing body of knowledge on indigenous textile use and students' fashion preference in Nigeria. Its findings is relevant to indigenous textile fabric manufacturers, fashion designers, cultural institutions and policymakers concerned with promoting Nigerian cultural heritage in sustaining the local textile industry. Understanding the perception and preferences of undergraduate students provides a basis for developing targeted strategies to promote indigenous fabrics in everyday fashion, promote cultural preservation, local economic development, and the reduction in dependence on imported fabrics.

1.6 The scope of the study

The study was limited to use of indigenous textile fabric (batik) for casual wears only among undergraduates at University of Agriculture, Abeokuta and of the Federal College of Education, Abeokuta.

1.7 Definition of term

Perception is how we interpret and understand the world around us through our senses.

Indigenous means the natural or originating home of an item; native.

Fabric is any cloth made yarn or fibres by knitting, weaving or felting.

Undergraduate is a college or university student studying for their first degree

Casual wear is any article of clothing suitable for informal occasions or situations.

Batik refers to a textile produced using a wax-resist dyeing technique in which hot wax is applied to fabric to prevent dye from penetrating selected areas, creating a pattern once the wax is removed.

CHAPTER TWO

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Understanding Batik as a Textile Tradition

Batik is one of many methods of decorating fabric. It is most commonly associated with Indonesia, where the technique was developed to a high level of sophistication, particularly on the island of Java. The technique involves applying hot wax to selected areas of a cloth before immersing the cloth in dye. Because the waxed areas repel the dye, a pattern is created when the wax is later removed. The process can be repeated multiple times to build up complex, multi-coloured designs (Webster, 1975).

The origins of batik are not entirely certain, but archaeological evidence suggests that forms of wax-resist dyeing were practised independently across South-East Asia, China, India, Japan, and West Africa over many centuries. Among these regions, Java developed the most intricate and elaborate batik tradition. Early scholarship suggested that the technique may have passed from China to Japan and from there into wider use across the region (Keyes-Adenaike, 1993).

Some researchers have linked batik to Hindu ritual practice, noting that certain patterns were used in ceremonies associated with birth, initiation, marriage, and death (Lindholm, 1989). Among the Sawu people of the Indonesian archipelago, batik cloth served as a means of social identification. In West Africa, particularly among the Yoruba of south-west Nigeria, the wax-resist tradition evolved into a distinct form known as adire, using locally sourced indigo dye and developing its own range of patterns, techniques, and cultural meanings (Eicher and Bubolz, 1986).

During the nineteenth century, Dutch textile mills began producing printed wax-cloth for the West African market. Small quantities of wax prints had earlier been introduced to West Africa by Christian missionaries, by European producers targeting the African market, and by West African soldiers who encountered Javanese batik during service in Indonesia (Nielson, 1990). By the early twentieth century, the export of printed cloth to West Africa had expanded rapidly, and Nigeria emerged as a significant centre of indigenous wax-resist textile production.

2.2 History of Batik and Adire in Abeokuta

Abeokuta occupies a particularly important place in the history of Nigerian indigenous textiles. As a centre of cotton production, weaving, and indigo dyeing during the nineteenth century, the city provided a strong foundation for the development of adire, a form of resist-dyed cloth that became closely identified with the city and its Egba Yoruba population (Byfield, 2002).

The earliest form of adire was a tie-dyed cloth known as kijipa, a handwoven fabric dyed with indigo and used primarily as wrappers and covering cloths. Female specialists were responsible for dyeing and for refreshing faded garments by re-dyeing with new patterns. When British trading firms flooded the West African market with cheap imported cotton shirting in the late nineteenth century, the adire industry responded creatively. Women discovered that the imported cloth was cheaper than handwoven fabric and could be decorated and dyed to meet local preferences. The smooth surface of the imported shirting proved particularly suitable for the development of new techniques, including stitch-resist adire alabere and hand-painted starch-resist adire eleko (Eicher and Bubolz, 1986).

By the early twentieth century, adire production in Abeokuta had reached a peak, and a wide trade network carried the cloth across West Africa. Senegalese merchants visited Abeokuta to purchase as many as 2,000 wrappers in a single day during the height of the trade in the 1920s (Byfield, 2002). During the 1930s, the introduction of new decorating techniques, including zinc stencilling and machine stitching, allowed men to enter an industry that had previously been dominated by women. Women retained control of the dyeing process, but men took up the decorating and finishing stages (Keyes-Adenaike, 1993).

A regional economic downturn at the end of the 1930s, combined with European export restrictions during the Second World War and the subsequent flooding of the market with cheap machine-printed cloth, led to a sharp decline in adire production. By the 1950s, few young people were learning the craft, and by the 1960s adire was increasingly regarded as the clothing of the poor in urban settings (Byfield, 2002).

The 1960s nonetheless marked a new phase of innovation in Yorubaland. The growing availability of chemical dyes from Europe introduced new colours and techniques, and Nigerian fashion designers adapted adire patterns for high-quality printed cloth. An expatriate woman named Betty Okuboyejo, based in Abeokuta, is credited with introducing a new range of commercial colour-fast dyes to Nigerian elites and expatriates, helping to revive interest in adire-inspired fabric (Eicher and Bubolz, 1986).

A simplified and widely produced version of adire, known as *kampala*, emerged in association with the Kampala Peace Conference during the Nigerian Civil War period. It was produced using basic wax-resist techniques by people with no prior training in dyeing, including farmers, traders, and the unemployed. Hot wax or paraffin replaced the traditional cassava paste as a resist agent, and designs were created through tie-dye, folding, and random wax application. Block printing techniques later developed from this tradition (Picton, 1995).

Today, contemporary adire and batik continue to evolve and appeal to fashion-conscious consumers in both urban and rural areas of Nigeria. Traditional indigo-dyed adire can still be found in specialist markets such as Oje Market in Ibadan, though it is increasingly sought by collectors rather than everyday buyers.

2.3 Colour Knowledge and Batik Design

Colour is central to the visual appeal and marketability of batik. An understanding of colour theory is essential for any batik designer who wishes to achieve quality results. Colour aesthetics may be understood from three perspectives, namely visual impression, emotional expression, and symbolic construction, and the study of colour in fabric design is grounded in the practical experience of artists and craftspeople (Oguntona, 1986).

Colours vary in their hue, value, and intensity, and the eye responds to these qualities in different ways (CESAC, 1980). Blue, as a primary colour, is cool and restrained, while red is warm and visually assertive. Yellow is the most luminous colour in the visible spectrum and represents brightness and purity. An effective batik designer must understand these qualities and how they interact when colours are combined, as poor colour combination produces dull or incoherent results.

Observations of small-scale batik producers in Abeokuta suggest that many lack formal training in colour theory, which affects the quality of their finished products (Oguntona, 1986). A further

production issue is the practice of drying finished batik in direct sunlight, which causes colours to fade and reduces the durability of the fabric. Best practice requires drying batik in shaded areas and avoiding harsh chemical detergents (Ijie, 2010). These practical quality considerations are directly linked to consumer perceptions of batik and to the fabric's competitiveness against imported alternatives.

2.4 The Impact of Cheap Imported Cloth

The Nigerian textile industry has been severely weakened by the influx of cheap imported fabrics from Asia, particularly China. According to estimates from the Nigerian Textiles and Clothing Workers Union, the industry lost 350,000 jobs directly and 1.5 million indirectly over a five-year period as a result of competition from Chinese-manufactured goods (Chiahemen, 2006). Warehouses that once stored locally manufactured textiles were converted to other uses because production had collapsed.

Several factors compounded this decline. High foreign exchange rates, inadequate infrastructure, rapid technological change in competing countries, insufficient capital, and limited market knowledge all weakened the ability of Nigerian producers to compete (Raw Materials Research and Development Council, 2002). Decades of military government left national institutions weakened and the economy poorly managed, creating conditions in which individual enterprise was difficult to sustain (Olukoyun, 2004).

Widespread poverty pushed many Nigerians towards the trade in second-hand imported clothing, commonly called Okrika. This trade required little start-up capital and offered quick returns, making it attractive to retrenched workers, students, and others with limited income (South African Institute of International Affairs, 2007). The spread of second-hand imported clothing further undermined the market for locally made textiles.

When Nigeria joined the World Trade Organisation in 1997, the government lifted its ban on textile imports in accordance with WTO obligations. This policy shift had an immediately harmful effect on local producers. The sector shrank from 137,000 jobs in 1997 to approximately 57,000 by 2003 (Olori, 2003). Imported textiles flooded the market at prices far below those of local goods, making it almost impossible for domestic producers to compete. By 2003, imported fabric accounted for roughly four times the quantity of locally produced textile, and much of it entered the country without paying full duties (Raw Materials Research and Development Council, 2002).

The consequences were not limited to economics. As consumers, including university students, turned to affordable imported fabrics, the cultural value attached to indigenous textiles such as batik declined. Consumer preference shifted towards foreign fabrics that were perceived as smarter and more fashionable, further reducing patronage of local producers (Muhammad, 2003). This economic and cultural context is essential for understanding the perceptions of batik found among undergraduate students in Abeokuta.

2.5 Strategies for Reviving Indigenous Textile Production

Researchers and industry analysts have identified niche marketing as a viable strategy for Nigerian batik and indigenous textile producers to remain competitive despite the pressure from cheap imports. Niche marketing involves concentrating on a well-defined market segment where quality, cultural identity, and uniqueness can command better prices and stronger loyalty than commodity producers can

offer (Linneman and Stanton, 1992). For indigenous batik producers, the cultural identity of the product and its association with Yoruba heritage represent precisely the kind of differentiation that a niche strategy can build upon.

Parrish, Cassil and Oxenham (2006) argued that firms in countries unable to compete on price alone must find ways to identify the most profitable market segments and build strong positions within them. For small-scale batik producers in Abeokuta, this might mean focusing on younger urban consumers who are interested in fashion, cultural expression, and authenticity.

Innovation is widely recognised as a key driver of competitiveness. Damanpour and Evans (1987) noted that innovation need not involve creating something entirely new; it can also mean introducing familiar ideas or techniques into new contexts. Walton (1987) argued that competition itself stimulates innovation, and that organisations operating in complex and unpredictable environments are encouraged to search for creative responses. For batik practitioners in Abeokuta, this suggests that adapting designs, techniques, and marketing approaches to meet contemporary student preferences represents a realistic and achievable path to growth.

Myers and Marquis (1969) emphasised that successful innovation must generate economic or social value and cannot be separated from an understanding of market needs. This reinforces the importance of studies such as this one, which examine the actual preferences and perceptions of potential consumers. Understanding what students want from casual wear, and how they currently perceive batik, is a necessary first step in developing effective strategies for promoting indigenous textile use.

2.6 Quality and Production Standards

Access to quality raw materials and the adoption of modern production techniques are central to the ability of Abeokuta's batik producers to compete in a demanding market. Poor quality materials and outdated production methods limit the consistency and appeal of finished products and make it difficult to sustain customer interest (Linneman and Stanton, 1992).

The introduction of modern equipment, such as electric cookers for melting wax, can improve production efficiency and reduce the physical demands on small-scale producers who currently rely on firewood. This change would also reduce the risk of inconsistent wax temperatures, which can affect design quality. Proper fabric drying practices, particularly avoiding direct sunlight, are also important for maintaining colour intensity and fabric life (Ijje, 2010). These improvements in production quality have a direct impact on how consumers, including undergraduate students, perceive and value locally produced batik.

CHAPTER THREE

3.0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research design

This study was a descriptive survey focused on the assessment of the use of indigenous textile (batik) for casual wear among the undergraduates of tertiary institution in Abeokuta, Ogun state.

The research design refers to the overall strategy that one chooses to integrate the different components of the study in a coherent and logical way, thereby ensuring one effectively addresses the research problem; it constitutes the blueprint for the data collection, measurement, and analysis of data.

3.2 Study Area

The study was carried out at University of Agriculture, Abeokuta and Federal College of Education, Abeokuta. University of Agriculture, Abeokuta was established by the Federal Government on January 1, 1988 when four Universities of Technology, earlier merged in 1984 were disbanded. It is one of the three specialized universities of Agriculture in Nigeria. The University started at its mini campus in Isale-igbehin in the Centre of Abeokuta, the capital of Ogun state. The university moved to its permanent site which is located next to the Ogun-Osun River Basin Development Authority (OORBDA) in October, 1993. The University started with Five Colleges which are; College of Agricultural Management, Rural Development and Studies (COLAMRUCS), College of Animal Science and Livestock Production (COLANIM), College of Environmental Resources Management (COLERM), College of Natural Sciences (COLNAS) and College of Plant Science and Crop Production (COLPLANT), two additional Colleges, (College of Engineering (COLENG) and College of Veterinary Medicine (COLVET) were introduced in March 2002 and May 1989 the first Council of the university was constitutionally headed by Alhaji Muhammadu Jega.

The Federal College of Education, Osiele, Abeokuta was established in 1976 as a Federal Advanced Teachers College, in addition to three similar colleges that were previously in existence at Okene, Pankshin and Yola. It is the first tertiary institution in Ogun State. The College started at the then Abeokuta Grammar School, Isale-Igbein. The College at inception shared the site with Abeokuta Grammar School until early January, 1978 when the school moved to its new site. school moved to its permanent site.

The Federal College of Education, Abeokuta provides three-year full-time and five-year sandwich courses respectively leading to the award of the Nigeria Certificate in Education [NCE]. The foundation day of the College is January 27, 1977, the day the first set of eighty-six students were registered after about four months of preparatory activities and assembling staff and equipment on site. This action gave practical effect to the Government plan and provisions in the 1976/1977 estimates for the establishment of an Advanced Teachers College at Abeokuta among others provided for, at other places during the year.

3.3 Population of the Study

The population of the study comprises of male and female undergraduate at University of Agriculture, Abeokuta. The university, with a population of close to 15,000 undergraduates and Federal college of Education, Abeokuta, with a population of close to 10,000 students.

3.4 Sample Size and Sampling technique

Using purposive sampling technique, a total of one hundred and twenty (120) were selected, sixty (60) from University of Agriculture and (60) sixty from FCE, Osiele.

3.5 Research Instrument

The instrument used for data collection was a structured questionnaire titled "Perception of Indigenous Fabrics (Batik) for casual wears: A study of undergraduate students' preference in Abeokuta".

The questionnaire had three (3) sections:

Section (A) consists of questions on personal data - age, sex, religion, level, estimated monthly income, ethnicity, household size.

Section (B) consists of eight (8) statement titled "the perception of the use of indigenous textile fabric batik for casual wears".

Section (C) consists of eleven (11) statement titled "form in which tertiary students use the indigenous textile fabric (batik)".

Respondent was expected to indicate their level of agreement or disagreement to the statements from: Strongly Agree-SA, Agree-A, Disagree-D, and Strongly Disagree-SD.

3.6 Validity of Research Instrument

The instrument was given to my supervisor and other expert in the field who ascertained that the instrument measured what it was supposed to measure. Base on the supervisor's advice and corrections, the final draft was prepare and used for data collection.

3.7 Reliability of the Research Instrument

A pilot study was carried out at Moshood Abiola polytechnic, Abeokuta where 15 pieces of the research instrument was administered. Reliability of instrument was accepted at a Cronbach Alpha value of 0.78.

3.8 Method of Data Collection

The method of data collection for the study was through survey. The survey method which consists of instrument design in form of questionnaire.

3.9 Method of Data Analysis

The data collected was subjected to descriptive statistical analysis, these include frequency distribution, percentages, mean, and standard deviation was used to present the data.

CHAPTER FOUR

4.0 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Shows the socio-economic characteristics of the respondents. As shown in the table, 21.7% of the respondents were less than 20 years old, 73.3% of them were less than 20 years old, 73.3% of them were in the age bracket of 21 - 30 years while 5.0% of them were in the age bracket of 31 - 40 years. The result also revealed that 44.2% of respondents were male and 55.8% were female. Christian respondents were 71.7%, 27.5% were Muslims and 0.8% practised African Traditional Religion (ATR). The majority of respondents, 32(26.7) were in 100 level, and the least number of respondents, 13(10.8) were in 300 level. Respondents in other levrls were 200 level (27, 22.5%), 400 level (23, 19.2%) and 500 level (25, 20.8%). The mean monthly allowance of respondents was ₦11,034 and the mean household size of respondents was 5 persons

Table 1: Socio-Economic Characteristics of Respondents (n = 120)

Characteristic	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age	Below 20 years	26	21.7
	21 to 30 years	88	73.3
	31 years and above	6	5.0
Sex	Male	53	44.2
	Female	67	55.8
Religion	Christian	86	71.7
	Muslim	33	27.5
	Traditional	1	0.8
Academic Level	100 level	32	26.7
	200 level	27	22.5
	300 level	13	10.8
	400 level	23	19.2
	500 level	25	20.8
Mean Monthly Allowance	N11,034		
Mean Household Size	5 persons		

4.2 Perception of the use of indigenous textile fabric batik for casual wear

Table 2 shows the perception of the respondents on the use of indigenous textile fabric (batik) for casual wears. Their perception towards the use of batik were ranked according to their means as follows: indigineous textile fabric batik at cheap to purchase compared to foreign fabrics ranked first with a mean value of (3.07), I prefer indigineous textile fabric batik to foreign fabric because of its reliability and durability ranked second, mean = 3.06, indigineous textile fabric batik lasts longer than foreign fabric with a mean of 2.88 ranked third, indigineous textile fabric batik makes me look smart (2.87), indigineous textile fabric batik is inferior to foreign fabric (2.81), foreign fabrics looks smarter than indigineous textile fabric batik had a mean values of (2.87) while African fabric is better demanded than any other type of fabrics ranked seventh with a mean value of

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Table 2: Perception of the use of indigenous textile fabric batik for casual wears among**(n=120)**

Strongly agree - SA, Agree - A, Disagree - D, Strongly disagree - SD

s/n	Statements	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Rank
1	I prefer African fabric to foreign fabric because of its reliability and durability	44 (36.0)	48 (40.0)	19 (15.8)	9 (7.5)	3.06	2
2	African fabrics are cheap to purchase compare to foreign fabrics	45 (37.5)	49 (40.0)	15 (12.5)	11 (9.2)	3.07	1
3	African fabric makes me look smart	33 (27.5)	51 (42.5)	24 (20.0)	12 (10.0)	2.87	4
4	African fabric is inferior to foreign fabrics	36 (30.0)	40 (33.3)	29 (24.2)	15 (12.5)	2.81	5
5	Foreign fabrics looks smarter than African fabrics	33 (27.5)	43 (35.8)	30 (25.0)	14 (11.7)	2.79	6
6	African fabrics last longer than foreign fabrics	34 (28.3)	34 (28.3)	40 (33.3)	7 (5.8)	2.79	6
7	African fabrics last longer than foreign fabrics	40 (33.3)	33	40 (33.3)	7 (5.8)	2.88	3
8	Africa fabrics is better demanded than any other type of fabrics	30	40 (33.3)	35	15 (12.5)	2.71	8

4.3 The factors responsible for the acceptability of the use of indigenous textile fabric

batik, for casual wear

Table 3 revealed the factors responsible for the acceptability of the use of indigenous textile fabric batik for casual wear. Decision of the respondents was ranked according to their mean as follows: Quality and durability (2.76), Cultural background (2.74), Individual consideration/preference(2.62), Societal influence (2.61), Expression of personality and identification (2.58), Comfortability (2.53), Environments (2.51),Social status (2.39).

Table 3: Factors responsible for the acceptability of the use of the indigenous textile fabric batik for casual wear. (n = 120)

Statements	Major Factor	Minor Factor	Not a factor	Mean	Rank
Quality and durability	92(75.7)	27(22.5)	1(0.8)	2.76	1st
Self-esteem and acceptance	73(60.8)	44(36.7)	3(2.5)	2.58	6th
Individual	81(67.5)	33(27.5)	6(5.0)	2.62	4th
Consideration / Preference	78(65.0)	34(28.3)	8(6.7)	2.58	6th
Expression of personality and identity	58(48.3)	45(37.5)	17(14.2)	2.34	11th
Peer group	72(60.0)	39(32.5)	9(7.5)	2.53	8th
Comforatbility	71(59.2)	38(31.7)	11(9.2)	2.50	9th
Environment	82(68.3)	29(24.2)	9(7.5)	2.61	5th
Societal influence	95(79.2)	19(15.8)	6(5.0)	2,74	2nd
Cultural background	83(69.2)	32(26.7)	5(4.2)	2.65	3rd
Social Status	59(49.2)	49(40.8)	12(10.0)	2.39	10th

4.4 Discussion

The result revealed 56.0% of the respondents were less than 30 years of age, the respondents. 30% of them were in the 31-40 age bracket with the mean age of 31 years. This implies that the majority of the respondents were youth and were still in their active age brackets.

Also the result revealed that 56.0% of them were female while 44.0% were male signifying that there were more female than male respondents in the study.

Majority 33 (27.5%) of respondents were students in Fourth year of education while the least number of respondents 8 (6.0%) were in their fifth year. Respondents in the first year of education were 28 (23.3%), second year of education was 25 (20.8%), and 26 (21.7%) were in the third year. Education is one factor that affects the choice of fashion style of an individual as educated people are more likely to wear contemporary fashion style compared to non-educated individuals. The findings also revealed that 91.0% of the respondents had an estimated monthly income less than one hundred thousand Naira. The financial status of an individual may determine the kind of fashion style they follow. Respondents engaged in different activities to generate income for themselves with 31 (25.8%) been traders, 19 (15.8%) were civil servants, 16 (13.3%) were into farming and 54 (45%) ran their own businesses.

The perceptions of the respondents on indigenous fabrics were rank according to the mean as follows:

indigenous fashion promotes cultural heritage (3.49). This implies that indigenous fashion styles promote cultural heritage.

The findings revealed that majority of the respondents agreed that indigenous fashion promotes cultural and ethnics unity (3.41)..This means that indigenous fashion styles indigenous fashion style s promote cultural and ethnics' unity.Also,majority of the agreed that indigenous fashion styles list longer than contemporary fashion respondents styles (3.24). This implies that indigenous fashion styles are more durable than the contemporary fashion to the contemporary fashion fashion styles. I prefer indigenous (3.21). This means that the respondents place more preference to indigenous fashion styles to contemporary fashion styles. Furthermore,majority of the respondent agreed that Indigenous fabrics are cheap to purchase(3.21). This implies that in terms of financial purchase, majority of the respondents prefer to go for indigenous fashion styles compare to contemporary fashion styles because of it availability and cheap amount to purchase them,whereby (Adesanya, 2013) study 51.7% strongly disagreed that they buy batik fabric.

However, majority of the respondents agreed that contemporary fabric styles last longer than indigenous fashion styles (2.73). Depicted from Adesanya (2013), 68.3% of respondents strongly disagree that they wear indigenous textile batik, this may be due to high quality of contemporary

fashion styles. Also, in considering the smartness and fitness of contemporary fashion styles to indigenous fashion styles majority of the respondents agreed that contemporary fabric looks smarter than indigenous (2.73). In considering the factors that influence the choice of fashion styles in Table 3 and Table 4. The result revealed that weather is more considered in wearing contemporary fashion styles (2.64) than indigenous fashion styles (2.32), which is in line with (Adesanya,2013) 46.7% prefer imported textiles to locally made batik. Social class is more considered in wearing contemporary fashion styles (2.84) than indigenous fashion styles (2.51). Customs and traditions is more considered in indigenous fashion styles (2.65) than contemporary fashion styles (2.43). This implies that customs and tradition is one of the major factors that promote the use of indigenous fashion styles than contemporary fashion styles, but Amubode's 2009 findings reveal that practitioners lack innovative ideas that can help them in the sustainable growth of their businesses and promote the socio-cultural advancement of their tradition.

CHAPTER FIVE

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

From the findings of this study, it was concluded that majority of respondents prefer to wear indigenous fashion styles to contemporary fashion styles. The study also found that some of the factors influencing the use of indigenous and contemporary fashion styles were environmental conditions, culture and custom, and social status,

5.2 Recommendation

Indigenous textile fabric batik is unique when designed and constructed with different beautiful materials to create intricate styles. It was observed from the study that the respondents often make use of Ankara, lace and other fabric materials when choosing fabric materials as casual wears while neglecting the indigenous made waxed resist dyed fabrics (batik). Some of the respondents have a biased mindset about indigenous textile fabric (batik).

The researcher recommends that: indigenous textile fabric should be prepared as a contemporary ready-made casual wears and other garments. However, there is a need to bring to their awareness the various convenient-to-use (contemporary) types that now exist and the great potentials each of them possess. In order for this development fashion exhibitions, trade fairs, and so on can be employed in institutions based on indigenous textile fabric batik for undergraduate students to see the glory and blessing for wearing our own indigenous textile fabric as day-to-day casual wears.

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